

REPOPSI's Submitted Application for the EOSC Future Grant

Call

RDA Open Call for cross disciplinary science adoption grants

Provider

EOSC Future

Proposal Title

TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology:
REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

Date Submitted

11 July 2022

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This report was created as part of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

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- [11. Provide a summary of the proposed work, how it is relevant to RDA. Outline the activities planned and associated timeline, the relationship to and impact on EOSC, and how an accompanying technical update can be created. Please also detail how the resources will be allocated e.g. on effort for staff, for how long, and other costs such as travel, etc.](#)
- [12. If you wish to submit accompanying information you can do so here via this upload link in a PDF format.](#)
- [13. LinkedIn / Personal Web page/Any other relevant link.](#)
- [14. Please upload your photo.](#)
- [15. Please upload your CV here.](#)
- [16. Please upload a brief project description, including its title.](#)
- [17. I agree to provide comms material to be published on the Grants Portal, including my photo, bio, name and project description \(title, 70-word abstract\).](#)
- [18. Declaration of confidentiality.](#)
- [19. I adhere to the RDA Guiding Principles and Code of Conduct.](#)
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1. Title of your proposal.

TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

2. Gender.

Female

3. Summary of involvement in RDA as contributor.

200 words max

Please provide a brief summary of previous and current activities demonstrating the applicant's community involvement and any additional contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest groups, development and/or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs in European Institutions throughout their communities.

We have used the RDA's TRUST principles for digital repositories to assess and improve the quality of an open repository for psychological instruments that we established called REPOPSI. In September 2020, we wrote a paper in English reporting the results of this self-assessment and, in October 2020, we were invited to present the paper at the Application of Free Software and Open Hardware Conference, organized by the University of Belgrade School of Electrical Engineering. We were also invited to contribute to the work of the RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group. In April 2021, we participated in the interest group's virtual session titled "From principles to metrics to evaluation, increasing TRUST in data repositories", organized at the RDA 17th Plenary Meeting. We gave a talk on the application of the TRUST principles to repository development and contributed to the session discussion. We advocated for our institution to publicly endorse the TRUST principles and, since October 2021, the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade in Serbia is included in the list of endorsers on the RDA website.

4. Your Domain Expertise.

Please select your area of domain expertise, you may select more than one. We are using the Frascati Classification mechanism. This helps us to get a full picture of the evaluator pool expertise range.

Natural sciences - Computer and information sciences, Social Sciences - other social sciences, Social sciences - Psychology and cognitive sciences

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5. Do you currently hold an RDA Open Call grant?

no

6. A statement describing the commitment to the vision of EOSC, the FAIR movement, national Open Science agendas (implementation), links to European data infrastructures or similar federated infrastructures.

1000 words max

The main goal of the proposed project is to improve the TRUSTworthiness of an open digital repository for psychology and to improve the FAIRness of the (meta)data it holds using RDA Recommendations and Outputs. In 2020, the applicants for this grant established the Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian – REPOPSI – at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade, Serbia). REPOPSI is hosted on the Open Science Framework platform at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>. It currently holds 176 instruments, including various psychological scales, tests, and questionnaires assessing personality, abilities, attitudes, etc. Improving such a repository directly aligns with the EOSC vision to enable scientific communities and research infrastructures towards FAIR management and reliable reuse of research data produced along the research life cycle (in this case, research instruments used to collect data from the participants).

REPOPSI is primarily intended for psychology researchers and students from the Bosnian-Croatian-Montenegrin-Serbian-language-speaking countries. However, as half of the instruments are currently available in both Serbian and English, it can also be used by cross-cultural research groups conducting large-scale projects. REPOPSI can be used freely without permission for clinical, research, and educational purposes under the Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license. Furthermore, anyone who wishes to deposit an original instrument in Serbian or a translation/adaptation of an instrument in Serbian can do so. During the first two years, the number of REPOPSI records has increased by 15% (progress report: <https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/repopsi-analytics/>), and is continuing to grow steadily. We set up a team of trained researchers and graduate students at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences who are in charge of maintaining the Repository. REPOPSI was established with no funding and continues to be run completely by volunteers. To provide a reliable, responsive, and consistent service, we rely on the FAIR Data (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) and the TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology) principles for self-assessment and improvement (the 2020 self-assessment is published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748545>).

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The majority of standardized psychological instruments have been originally created in English and need to be translated and adapted to other countries and cultural contexts. Before REPOPSI, there were no centralized open repositories for the translations and adaptations of psychological instruments in Serbian. REPOPSI, therefore, greatly improves the findability, reusability, and visibility of this type of research data. It streamlines the research process by making it easier to collect, find, reuse, and preserve the translations. It also prevents overlapping translation/adaptation efforts, which were common in the past. REPOPSI allows local researchers to contribute their own original instruments or translations, offering them the opportunity to reach a wider audience. It also makes it easier for researchers to share their tools, contributing to the overall transparency and reproducibility of the research process.

REPOPSI has proven useful in teaching and learning (e.g. students can now quickly find instruments to carry out class or thesis projects) as well as in large-scale, multi-site collaborations by providing access to instruments that have already been translated and prepared for cross-cultural research. REPOPSI is listed in the Registry of Research Data Repositories - re3data.org (<http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMV5>) and on the map of repositories curated by the National Open Science Portal of Serbia (<https://open.ac.rs/index.php/repozitorijumi>). REPOPSI has recently been recognized as one of the good practices of Responsible Research and Innovation from the Western Balkans (<https://wbc-rti.info/object/link/22747>).

Research data repositories such as REPOPSI are an essential part of a country's Open Science infrastructure. This proposal, therefore, ties into Serbia's Open Science Platform (<https://eosc-portal.eu/serbia-open-science-platform>) adopted in 2018, a policy which encourages open-access sharing of research data. Furthermore, some of the project efforts will be focused on diversifying the potential pool of measurement instruments for the Repository by searching the data associated with conference papers and dissertations, moving away from journal articles, which have been the most common source so far. In doing so, we will rely on existing Open Science infrastructures in Serbia, such as the National Repository of Dissertations in Serbia.

The project team will include one project manager and a group of four project consultants who will contribute their expertise in different areas, including Open Science principles and data stewardship. The project manager and three of the consultants are affiliated with the Department of Psychology at the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy; they were the core team responsible for founding the Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian – REPOPSI. They share a history of previous collaboration on Big Team and Open Science projects, such as the influential “Many Labs” crowdsourced Replications Projects in psychological science. The Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences, where they work, has been committed to the principles of Open Science for many years, promoting transparency,

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credibility, reproducibility, and accessibility (<https://lira.f.bg.ac.rs/en/open-science-and-cross-cultural-studies/>). The fourth project consultant will be a Library Manager, employed at the University of Belgrade Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, who has expert knowledge in research data management. Some of the project team members have recently completed the EOSC funded co-creation activity "Boosting EOSC readiness: Creating a scalable model for capacity building in RDM" (technical report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4696595>). The team members have held a number of lectures and workshops devoted to the topic of Open Science and research data management, both for the local and international audience. They are active in organizations such as the RDA, Collaborative Replications and Education Project, and Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training. Last year, two of the project team members co-founded the Open Science Community Serbia (<https://oscs.open.ac.rs/>).

7. A brief summary of previous and current activities demonstrating the applicant's involvement and contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest Groups, development and/or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs in European Institutions.

1000 words max

As members of RDA, we have been involved in the adoption and promotion of RDA's TRUST Principles for digital repositories. We have used the TRUST principles presented in Lin et al. (2020) Scientific Data article (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>) to assess and improve the quality of an open repository we established at our academic institution – the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade in Serbia. This repository is called REPOPSI (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>) and it stores open-access psychological measurement instruments (e.g. scales, questionnaires, tests) translated into Serbian, adapted for the Serbian population, or developed by local scientists. Since its launch in March 2020, we have continually used the TRUST principles to assess the trustworthiness of our Repository with respect to transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability, and technology. This includes using the TRUST principles as guidelines for planning Repository improvements. In September 2020, we wrote a paper in English reporting the results of this self-assessment and, in October 2020, we were invited to present the paper at the Application of Free Software and Open Hardware Conference, organized by the University of Belgrade School of Electrical Engineering. The conference paper and the slides from the talk are available open-access at: Lazić, A., Lazarević, L. B., Purić, D., & Žeželj, I. (2021). REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian. 51–56. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748545>. The recording of the conference talk in English is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BWC5cMSZ6sw>. Based on this conference

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paper, we were invited to contribute to the work of the RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories Interest Group. In April 2021, we participated in the interest group's virtual session titled "From principles to metrics to evaluation, increasing TRUST in data repositories", organized at the RDA 17th Plenary Meeting. We gave a talk on the application of the TRUST principles to repository development and contributed to the session discussion. The talk is available at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-vp17-certification-digital-repositories-ig-presentations> and the slides are available open-access at: Lazić, A., Lazarević, L. B., Purić, D., & Žeželj, I. (2021, April 21). REPOPSI's perspective on the TRUST principles. Research Data Alliance 17th Plenary Meeting (RDA VP17), Edinburgh (Virtual). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4708281>. We advocated for our institution to publicly endorse the TRUST principles and, since October 2021, the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade in Serbia is included in the list of endorsers on the RDA website at: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-community-effort-trust-principles-digital-repositories>.

8. Please provide a short abstract of your proposed project.

100 words max

REPOPSI is an open digital repository for psychological research instruments, such as questionnaires and tests, established and maintained by the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy in Serbia. By implementing RDA recommendations and other outputs, this project aims to improve REPOPSI's TRUSTworthiness as well as the FAIRness of its (meta)data. The project focuses on building the Repository's technologies needed to improve its adherence especially to the principles of User Focus, Sustainability, Findability, and Interoperability. Dissemination and community activities are designed to promote further uptake of RDA outputs.

9. Describe the impact of your proposal in terms of how it benefits cross-disciplinary collaboration and the community around EOSC, contribution to EOSC i.e. RDA output(s) made useful in EOSC, relevance for EOSC Future e.g., Proposed core-service use.

1500 words max

The proposed project will demonstrate how RDA standards/recommendations can be leveraged to improve the managing and sharing of research data, specifically to improve the FAIRness and TRUSTworthiness of a community-led open digital repository for psychological research instruments – REPOPSI. It will show how the "CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements: Extended Guidance 2020–2022" document (CoreTrustSeal Standards and

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Certification Board; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632532>) can be used to assess the organizational infrastructure, digital object management, and technology of smaller-scale open repository in psychology, as well as how the “FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines” document (RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group; <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>) can be used to assess the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of the Repository’s data. Furthermore, the project will pilot the application of a discipline-specific metadata thesaurus that follows the FAIR principles. Overall, the project will demonstrate how to make research data more FAIR and how to make an open repository more TRUSTworthy within a social science discipline (psychology), highlighting interoperability issues. The final legs of the project will include (a) applying for the CoreTrustSeal (www.coretrustseal.org) certification and (b) adding the improved Repository as a new database entry in the FAIRsharing.org Registry, describing it with the help of the “FAIRsharing Standards, Repositories and Policies: facilitating discovery, adoption and use” Executive Summary of the Adopted Recommendation of the joint RDA-Force11 FAIRsharing Working Group (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fairsharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-and-databases-rda-wg/outcomes>). These activities will further demonstrate the adoption of RDA standards/recommendations and the integration of psychological research data into an existing data catalog, while also making the Repository more discoverable, more widely adopted and cited. The project will result in several published works detailing the challenges to sharing instruments as a type of research data in psychology, with suggested solutions and requirements, including blog posts on the new Repository website and the RDA Adoption Stories page (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>), as well as a conference presentation at an EOSC/RDA-supported event (e.g. the 10th Anniversary RDA Plenary Meeting in Gothenburg or the EOSC Symposium 2022 in Prague). More locally, the project will widen EOSC engagement and RDA standards/recommendations adoption in an institution based in South-Eastern Europe by organizing a local workshop and by training junior student assistants and involving them in project realization.

Repositories such as REPOPSI improve the findability, reusability, and visibility of research data. This Repository, already well adopted and recognized, will become even more beneficial to its target user community after the realization of the proposed activities. For example, the new Repository website we will build will ensure that important information such as the mission statement, scope, and terms of use are more transparently declared and more easily accessed by the users (especially by those who are less familiar with the Open Science Framework platform the Repository currently solely relies on). By making the Repository contribution form available as an online survey embedded on the new Repository website, the contribution procedure will become more efficient, leaving less room for omissions and errors on the users’ part. Moreover, by carrying out the planned activities involving the search for existing

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instruments and contacting instrument authors directly, the Repository will move away from relying solely on contributions from individual researchers and students, making the process more proactive and efficient. The new search and download interface in the form of a web app that will be built during the project will automate the search of the Repository metadata, currently stored in a dataset on the Repository's OSF project page. As such, the web app will not only improve the machine-readability of the Repository (meta)data but will also provide the users with an additional and a more efficient way to search the Repository. Similarly, adding a controlled vocabulary (thesaurus) to the metadata will not only provide a consistent way to describe the Repository contents and increase Repository interoperability but will also facilitate search and browsing. By testing the prototypes of the new website and the search and download interface with the users from the target community, we will increase Repository usability and user experience, making it an environment that responds to real user needs.

10. Describe the sustainability and impact potential of the proposal and how this can be carried forward within the context of EOSC and RDA. Applicants should put forward plans for expected uptake and maintenance. Methodology of application: The proposal must be thought through, well-written, clear and demonstrate the methodology works.

1500 words max

The impact of the proposed project will continue even after the grant has ended. The planned dissemination activities such as the blog posts, social media promotion, and workshops will not only increase the visibility of the Repository and the RDA standards/recommendations, but will also serve an educational purpose. These activities will raise the awareness of the importance of opening research data and encourage the community to learn more about repository TRUSTworthiness and data FAIRness, empowering them to implement these principles to their own research materials and deposit their research instruments into the Repository in the future. Furthermore, we will make sure that the dissemination activities reach relevant actors. We will organize a workshop with the support of the Open Science Community Serbia since we have previous experience of organizing such events (in April 2022, we held an online workshop on searching the Repository and contributing to it, attended by psychology students, researchers, and librarians; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6460259>) and we will use established social media channels for the promotional activities. We have already actively promoted the Repository on our Laboratory's Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn accounts, with the majority of the audience being Repository users from Serbia as well as potential stakeholders from other countries. All of the previous posts are available under the hashtag #REPOPSI (on Facebook at <https://www.facebook.com/hashtag/repopsi>; on Twitter at https://twitter.com/hashtag/REPOPSI?src=hashtag_click; and on LinkedIn at

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<https://www.linkedin.com/search/results/content/?keywords=repopsi>). Another way to carry forward the impact of the project will be through the trained student assistants engaged in finding and depositing existing instruments. They will become more versed in research data management using the Repository and will be able to pass that knowledge to their peers.

Apart from benefitting the individuals, the project has the potential to benefit other academic institutions that wish to implement RDA standards/recommendations, especially in the domain of social sciences. We will provide all project products and documentation, including, for example, the new Repository website and the blog posts, in both Serbian and English, making the project outputs more accessible to a wider audience. All of the outputs will also be made public and transparent, so that they are easily used, transferred or replicated. The project will, therefore, continue to encourage adoption of RDA standards/recommendations in similar communities even after the grant has ended.

We will secure the hosting infrastructure of the new Repository website and web app by paying for the hosting for the maximum allowed time in advance (three years in the case of the website and six years in the case of the web app). Furthermore, we will make sure that the website is created using a platform we already know how to use (e.g. WordPress) so that we can later update it and maintain it by ourselves. We decided to have the web app built using the R programming environment because it is a free software and because our team members have ample previous experience of working in R. The team members will be trained on how to use and update the web app so that they are able to maintain it by themselves in the future.

After the project has ended, the team members will have gained the skills and knowledge needed to plan for future Repository maintenance. For example, the planned CoreTrustSeal application procedure will be beneficial even if the Repository is not ultimately awarded the certification because it will provide us with additional evaluation by external professionals, and thus an independent insight on how the Repository may evolve to further increase its trustworthiness. Furthermore, the RDA/EOSC events bring together a global community of data science and stewardship professionals and researchers working in multiple disciplines; attending such an event will allow us to expand our network and learn about new trends and policies.

Given these sustainability precautions and the fact that the Repository data are hosted on the free-of-cost Open Science Framework platform that has an established preservation fund, we are confident that the Repository and the outputs resulting from this project will be publicly available for a long time, thus increasing the visibility of the RDA standards/recommendations we have adopted and implemented during the project lifetime.

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11. Provide a summary of the proposed work, how it is relevant to RDA. Outline the activities planned and associated timeline, the relationship to and impact on EOSC, and how an accompanying technical update can be created. Please also detail how the resources will be allocated e.g. on effort for staff, for how long, and other costs such as travel, etc.

1500 words max

The project activities are grouped around three goals and will be carried out over the course of nine months. For a detailed project timeline, please see the attached PDF. The total requested budget for this project is €49,748.58. For a detailed breakdown of the costs, please see the attached PDF.

GOAL 1 is to improve the TRUSTworthiness of the REPOPSI repository and the FAIRness of its (meta)data.

The OBJECTIVES for GOAL 1 are to (1-A) create the Repository website; (1-B) create an online contribution form; (1-C) create a search and download interface; (1-D) pilot applying a controlled vocabulary; and (1-E) implement specific RDA Recommendations and Outputs for the self-assessment and planning of the realization of the aforementioned objectives.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 1-A, we will hire a professional to create a website and pay for the hosting for three years in advance. The website is important because it will provide the technology necessary to realize almost all of the other activities. The “About”, “Contact”, and “Our Team” pages on the website will organize the information currently laid out on the repository’s Wiki page – which is part of its Open Science Framework (OSF) project – including its mission statement, scope, and terms of use. Once the website is live, we will create a redirect link on the Repository’s OSF page so that its visitors are automatically redirected from the page to the new website. The entire contents of the website will be provided in both Serbian and English.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 1-B, we will embed an online survey form on the “Contribute” page of the website, which potential contributors will have to fill in to submit their original psychological instruments or instrument translations/adaptations to the Repository. We have already developed this form but it is currently available only as a Google Sheet that the users have to request from the Laboratory via email. The website will allow the visitors to create an account granting them the rights to access the “Contribute” page. We will test a prototype of the “Create a Contributor Account” and “Contribute” pages with the users from the target community.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 1-C, we will hire a professional to create a web application for searching the Repository contents. The web app will be created using the Shiny package for the

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R programming environment. The web app will automate the search of the Repository's metadata and users will be able to access it via the "Search the Repository" website tab redirecting to it. We will test a prototype of the web app with the users from the target community. We will hire the same professional to also hold a training session for the team on the use and maintenance of the Shiny web app. We will pay for the shinyapps.io Basic Plan for six years in advance; this plan allows for 500 active user hours per month and can support multiple people using the web app at the same time.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 1-D, we will apply an existing, universally agreed upon controlled vocabulary (thesaurus) to the Repository. This vocabulary will follow the FAIR principles and will come from the social sciences domain. We will apply the standardized set of terms from the vocabulary to existing records and integrate the vocabulary with the Contribution form so that new records are routinely described in a uniform way.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 1-E, we will implement the following RDA Recommendations and Outputs for self-assessment and detailed planning: (a) the "CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements: Extended Guidance 2020–2022" document (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632532>) and (b) the "FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines" document (RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group; <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>). We will perform the trustworthiness and the fairness assessment once at the start and once at the end of the project. During the last months of the project, we will apply for the CoreTrustSeal (www.coretrustseal.org) certification.

GOAL 2 is to disseminate the activities and the outputs of our work during the project lifetime.

The OBJECTIVES for GOAL 2 are to (2-A) write three public blog posts; (2-B) organize a local online workshop; (2-C) attend an RDA/EOSC event abroad; (2-D) promote the project on social media; and (2-E) add the Repository to FAIRsharing.org Registry.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 2-A, we will designate a "Blog" page on the newly created Repository website. The team will write one blog post, aimed at the general public, that will describe the mission and development of the Repository and the impact of the grant. We will also write two blog posts, aimed at social science researchers and librarians, in which we will share our experience with implementing specific RDA Recommendations and Outputs for Repository self-assessment and development. The blog will be licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International. We will provide the blog posts in both Serbian and English. We will also prepare one story based on these blog posts and share it on the RDA Adoption Stories page (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>).

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To achieve the OBJECTIVE 2-B, we will hold an online workshop with the support of the Open Science Community Serbia (oscs.open.ac.rs). The workshop for this project will be focused on promoting RDA Recommendations and Outputs we used during the project and on sharing the lessons learned with relevant stakeholders in Serbia. The slides and other workshop materials in Serbian will be openly shared on Zenodo, under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 2-C, the team will attend an event organized by the RDA or EOSC, such as the 10th Anniversary RDA Plenary Meeting in Gothenburg or the EOSC Symposium 2022 in Prague. Such an event will be an opportunity for us to share project updates, present our RDA adoption case story, discuss barriers and potential solutions.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 2-D, we will regularly post about the outputs of this project (e.g. the Repository website, workshop, blog) on our Laboratory's social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn.

To achieve the OBJECTIVE 2-E, towards the end of the project, we will add the improved Repository as a new database entry in the FAIRsharing.org Registry. To best describe this resource, we will use the "FAIRsharing Standards, Repositories and Policies: facilitating discovery, adoption and use" Executive Summary of the Adopted Recommendation of the joint RDA-Force11 FAIRsharing Working Group (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fairsharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-and-databases-rda-wg/outcomes>).

GOAL 3 is to improve the completeness of the data in the Repository.

The OBJECTIVES for GOAL 3 are to (3-A) search dissertations in psychology; (3-B) search proceedings from conferences in Serbia; and (3-C) contact the authors of existing psychological instruments that have not been already deposited in the Repository.

To achieve OBJECTIVES 3-A, 3-B and 3-C we will hire three psychology undergraduate or (post)graduate students at the Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade as project assistants. We will hold a training session for them on where and how to search the data, how to decide whether the instrument can be deposited in the Repository, and how to fill out the contribution form. We will organize monthly meetings to share progress updates. The student assistants will search the National Repository of Dissertations in Serbia (nardus.mpn.gov.rs), where all dissertations have been required to be made publicly available since 2014. They will also search the collections of conference papers in the digital archive of the annual Empirical Studies in Psychology Conference (empirijskaistrazivanja.org), available since 2013. Being the largest psychological conference in the region, it gives access to a large pool of relevant studies conducted in the Bosnian-Croatian-Montenegrin-Serbian language, some of which have not (yet)

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been published in journals. Depending on the number instruments retrieved this way, and if time allows, the student assistants may also search for other sources of data. For example, they may search public theses repositories such as the DART-Europe E-theses Portal (www.dart-europe.org) or look into other conference archives. To achieve the OBJECTIVE 3-C, the hired students will be instructed to contact the corresponding authors in case the information provided in the dissertations and conference papers they have found is not sufficient to adequately deposit the instrument in the Repository.

12. If you wish to submit accompanying information you can do so here via this upload link in a PDF format.

repopsi_proposal_budget.pdf

repopsi_proposal_timeline.pdf

13. LinkedIn / Personal Web page/Any other relevant link.

REPOPSI, the open Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>

The Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (Faculty of Philosophy University of Belgrade, Serbia): <https://lira.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>

14. Please upload your photo.

repopsi_proposal_team-photo.png

15. Please upload your CV here.

repopsi_proposal_CVs.pdf

16. Please upload a brief project description, including its title.

70 words max

“TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs”. By implementing RDA recommendations and other outputs, this project aims to improve the TRUSTworthiness of an open digital repository for psychological research instruments in Serbian (REPOPSI) as well as the FAIRness of its (meta)data. Dissemination and community activities are designed to promote further uptake of RDA outputs.

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17. I agree to provide comms material to be published on the Grants Portal, including my photo, bio, name and project description (title, 70-word abstract).

I accept to sign a declaration of confidentiality

18. Declaration of confidentiality.

I accept to sign a declaration of confidentiality

19. I adhere to the RDA Guiding Principles and Code of Conduct.

Yes

20. Declaration of Honour.

I am not directly working on EOSC Future project activities (i.e. directly funded through a beneficiary (its department or unit executing EOSC Future activities), as a LTP or seconded personnel).

21. Use of personal information.

Accept

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